

**ANALYSIS OF POSTCOLONIAL CRITICAL THEORY AS AN ANTI-COLONIAL
METHOD: BHARATI MUKERJI'S 'JASMINE' AS A PROTOTYPE.**

T.Narayana, Lecturer in English, Government Degree College (A), Ananthapuram, Research
Scholar, K.L.University, Guntur.

Dr.S.N.Shamabharathi Lecturer in English, Government Degree college, Ananthapuram.

Abstract: A "literary theory" is a set of concepts and intellectual assumptions that are used to explain or interpret literary texts. Postcolonial theory is a literary critical approach that focuses on literature produced in countries that were or are currently colonies of other countries. It may also deal with literature written in or by citizens of colonizing countries about colonies, people and their problems. The aim of the present paper is, as a contemporary critical theory, postcolonial theorists questions the European hegemony and as a school of thought it focuses on i) the political, aesthetic, economic, historical, and social consequences of European colonial rule around the world, ii) the anti-colonial struggles of the Third World and the rise of nationalism; iii) and the creation of mimic. The objectives of the paper are i) to explore the important critics of the theory, their works, and key terms. ii) to connect the plot and structure of Bharati Mukerji's novel "Jasmine" to postcolonial critical theory The study also shows that the works that are written in post colonial period are to be analyzed by the approach. The method of study is to revise the prominent writers and their texts, secondary critical texts, and to read available articles.

Key words: postcolonial, anti colonial, approach, colony, nationalism, third world.

Introduction: Literature encompasses both written and spoken material. It is most commonly used to describe works of the creative imagination, such as poetry, drama, fiction, nonfiction, and, in some cases, journalism. Literature exists to entertain and to provide aesthetic pleasure. We can learn more about cultures and appreciate them more. Manuscripts and oral history, for example, teach us about history. The purpose of this paper is to show that writers, while contributing different aspects to literature, follow a set of rules from time to time.

In general, criticism can be defined as a "discourse about literature." Literary criticism refers to the study, discussion, evaluation, and interpretation of literature. It is an act of researching, debating, evaluating, and interpreting. Literary theory is the philosophical discussion of the methods and goals of literary criticism, and each literary theory provides its own unique perspective on a piece of literature. The literary theory combines literature with theory or philosophy about literature. The reading of a literary text is done through a window. Each school of thought and theory has its own specific understanding of the function of the literary text. It emerges from a tradition.

A theorist's job is to shape up these aspects related to particular theory. It is stated, even if a critic was not a theorist; he would clearly reflect the temperament of his times. There has been a steady emergence of a number of theories. The majority of criticism is now based on theory. There are numerous "schools" or types of literary theory, which takes various approaches to understanding texts. The majority of these theories originated on the continent, though they have grown steadily in the United Kingdom and the United States.

Literary theory is a broad field today. It encompasses a diverse range of approaches used by humanities, researchers to investigate literary texts. It also refers to the teaching of such approaches and practices in universities, specifically in English departments. Texts from a wide range of disciplines, such as linguistics, anthropology, politics, philosophy, psychoanalysis, and other related disciplines are applied to the investigation of the literary text.. Often, the critical canons of one age have been abandoned entirely, only to be revived by a subsequent age. Thus, the principles of criticism are the various interpretations of literature or literary activities that have been advanced over time. They are similar at times, dissimilar at others, and even contradictory at times.

The art of criticism in Europe began with ancient Greece. The ancient Greeks pioneered two types of criticism: theoretical, which, like **Plato** and **Aristotle**, attempts to state general principles about the value of art, and practical, which examines specific works, genres, or writers in light of theoretical principles. Horace and Longinus used the same criteria. In the **Preface to the State of Innocence**, Dryden stated that criticism, as first instituted by Aristotle, meant a standard of good judgment. The term "good" was first used in **Pope's Essay on Criticism**. Because the general tone of neoclassical criticism was prescriptive, it is referred to as judicial criticism. In his **Defense of Poetry**, Philip Sydney argued that poetry must engage and uplift the emotions of its audience. Johnson's **Lives of the Poets** was the first comprehensive study of biographical criticism.

The mid-nineteenth-century criticism was characterized by a variety of trends. Matthew Arnold's **didacticism**, which held that the goals of literature should be "**high seriousness**" and "**criticism of life.**" The critics Edgar Allan Poe, Walter Pater, and Arthur Symons praised art for its own sake. Aesthetic criticism views literature as an independent activity with a goal of its own, which may or may not coincide with religion, morality, science, or philosophy politics. As a result, it investigates the nature of literary art in general and formulates its conclusions.

The twentieth century was designated the "Age of Criticism." Major disciplines such as psychology, anthropology, and Marxism were discovered to have valid applications to literary works. Freudian analysis became literary tool biographers. Carl Jung's theory of the collective unconscious, as well as for critics such as T. S. Eliot in *The Sacred Wood*, anthropological methodology was used. Northrop Frye in **Anatomy of Criticism**, who attempted to draw parallels between pattern in literature from various cultures and I. A. Richard, employed techniques from psychological measurement to investigate reader response with greater precision, most notably in *Practical Criticism*. Critics such as Cleanthes Brooks, Allen Tate, Lionel Trilling, and John Crow followed the technique of close examination of the text.

Method: The study employs a qualitative approach, analyzing prominent critics, critical books, articles, journals, theses, dissertations, and e-content in the postcolonial arena.

Literary review: The critical book on critical methods entitled **A Handbook of Critical Approaches**, Oxford University was reviewed. The critical book offers readers a variety of clearly articulated approaches to interpreting literature, ranging from traditional approaches to the most contemporary perspectives, such as feminist and gender studies, cultural studies, and postcolonial studies.

i) Edward Said's notable critical work **Orientalism** was reviewed. The study of the Orient or the Eastern world is known as Orientalism. According to Said, Orientalism arose as a result of the West's need to define itself as the polar opposite of a counter balancing entity. The book examines the impact of this belief system on the relationships between Eastern and Western nations

ii) Edward Said's another critical work entitled, **Cultural Imperialism** was reviewed. According to Edward Said, culture is a country's identification. Imperialism, on the other hand, is nothing more than a desire for power, resources, and land; thus, it destroys the identity/culture.

iii) Gyathri Chakravarty Spivac's critical book **Postcolonial Reason** was reviewed it traces the "native informant" through various cultural practices: philosophy, history, literature, to suggest that it emerges as the metropolitan hybrid. The book addresses feminists, philosophers, critics, and interventionist intellectuals as they unite and divide

iv) Homi K. Bhabha lays out the conceptual, essential and political consistency of a postcolonial intellectual project in **The Location of Culture**. In a brilliant series of interdisciplinary essays, he explains why Western modernity's culture must be relocated from a postcolonial perspective.

v) Homi K. Bhabha in his **Hybridity and Discursive** says, 'in-between' space that bears the burden and meaning of culture, which is why the concept of hybridity is so important. In postcolonial discourse, hybridity has frequently been used to mean simply cross-cultural "exchange."

vi) Fanon in his **Wretched of the Earth** contends that the colonized intellectual must recognize that a national culture does not exist as a historical reality waiting to be discovered in a return to pre-colonial history and tradition, but rather exists in the present national reality.

vii) A research article on the development of critical theories entitled as A Critical Overview of Literary Criticism in English Literature by simhachalam Thamarana was reviewed

Objectives:

- ❖ to understand the basic concepts of literary criticism
- ❖ to appreciate the value of literature
- ❖ to estimate the history of literary criticism
- ❖ to recognize the various literary critical theories
- ❖ to identify the function of a critical theory
- ❖ to comprehend the theory of post colonial
- ❖ to make out important critics and their contribution to post colonial theory
- ❖ to classify the various terms related to post colonial critical theory
- ❖ . to distinguish Diaspora writings deal with the effects of post colonialism
- ❖ to consider Bharathi Mukejee's *Jasmine* as a postcolonial novel

Result: The process of analyzing and evaluating the quality of a work of literary writing is implicitly defined as criticism. Critical methods have evolved over time to reflect current social realities. Postcolonial critics focused on the effects of colonialism, resulting in the understanding of new terms associated with it. Said, Spivac, and Homibaba are also thought to have contributed to postcolonial studies. As it focuses on the writers' motherland's problems, there will be plenty of room for Diaspora writings.

Discussion: "Literary theory" is the body of ideas, set of concepts, assumptions and methods on which rests the work of explaining or interpreting literary texts we use in the practical reading of literature. All literary interpretation draws on a basis in theory but can serve as justification for very different kinds of critical activity. Literary theorists of the twentieth century undoubtedly followed outfit.. Literary theory and criticism can help us by shedding light on the underlying meanings. With the right tools, one can gain a deep understanding of the texts one reads and approach literature's most menacing topics with confidence. This article offers a plethora of background information and insightful analysis post colonial critical theory to assist you in making use of literary theory and criticism in a variety of contexts.

- Recognize the themes, symbols, and motifs in a text.
- Examine an author's writing style.
- Write a critical essay or book analysis.
- Engage in a thorough literary discussion.

Post colonialism is a critical examination of the history, culture, literature, and modes of discourse in Third World countries in Africa, Asia, the Caribbean Islands, and South America. It is concerned with the study of colonization, decolonization and the neocolonising. Post colonialism examines the metaphysical, ethical, and political concerns about cultural identity, gender, nationality, race, ethnicity, subjectivity, language, and power, with a focus on the omnipresent power struggles between cultures and the intersection of cultures, which results in multiculturalism and poly valiancy of culture.

Postcolonial literary criticism, influenced by the poststructuralist and postmodern concept of decent ring, undermines the Universalist claims of literature, identifies colonial sympathies in the canon, and replaces colonial meta narratives with counter-narratives of resistance, by rewriting history and asserting cultural identities through strategies such as separatism, nativism, cultural relativism, and cultural relativism, cultural syncretism, hybridity, mimicry, active participation and assimilation.

Postcolonial theory has brought fresh perspectives to the role of colonial peoples in the development of modern European nation states. The increasing globalization of culture, including the neo-colonialism of multinational capitalism, suggests a continued relevance for this field of inquiry.

It criticizes cultural hierarchies and modernity's Euro centrism, based on an anti-essentialist notion of identity and culture. The major theoretical works in postcolonial theory include Franz Fanon's **The Wretched of the Earth**, Edward Sad's **Orientalism**, Gayatri Spivak's **In Other Worlds**, Bill Ashcroft et al's **The Empire Writes Back**, Homi K Bhabha's **Nation and Narration**, and Edward Said's **Culture and Imperialism**. Edward Said's **Orientalism** is regarded as having inaugurated the field of "Postcolonial Criticism" in the West. Indigenous peoples from previously colonized and marginalized countries are increasingly finding their voices in literature, attempting to assert their own visions, tell their own stories, and reclaim their experiences and histories.

Euro centrism, also known as Europe-centricity, refers to the ways in which European cultural assumptions are constructed as normal and natural as well as universal. This term has been in use since the beginning of the twentieth century in various disciplines but gained fame throughout the 1990s. During the colonial period, European imperialist powers facilitated Euro centrism through exploration, conquest, and trade. It was later carried out by other means. Media such as education, religion, culture, race, and so on. The plan's supporters were aware that they were positing European ideas are considered superior to all other ideas. Following that, From then on, the sense of 'otherness' was infused into the colonized people's minds.

Edward Said: Within the framework of Postcolonial studies, Palestinian-American scholar Edward Said wrote his famous work **Orientalism**, in which he criticizes Western-based representations of the East and emphasizes how knowledge and discourse are linked with power to define and name the Orient. **Orientalism** was a book about a specific pattern in Western thought. It was not an assessment of the significance of that thought in and of itself. It was written before the academic "culture wars," when key words like relativism, pluralism, and multiculturalism were the order of the day. Said has frequently been lumped in with relativists and pluralists, but he does not belong there.

Orientalism was ultimately a political vision of reality whose structure promoted the difference between the familiar (Europe, West, "us") and the strange (the Orient, the East, "them")."

Said generally avoided provoking language in his later literary and cultural work, particularly in **Culture and Imperialism**. Whereas others have angrily rejected the Western Canon's literary heritage, Said, though ambivalently, has embraced it. Joseph Conrad and Rudyard Kipling were condemned as racist dead white men, Said wrote careful reappraisals of their works, focusing on their representations of India and Africa, respectively. Said deduces the ins and outs of Conrad's **The Heart of Darkness** from a postcolonial perspective

Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak: Spivak asserts that the subaltern subject is heterogeneous, and that by investigating the mechanisms of their ostensible "recovery" of their voice, he discovers an ongoing displacement and effacement. Spivak's central subject position is that of the female subaltern and the practice of sati, or widow immolation. She argues that a core problem for the poorest and most marginalized in society (the subalterns) is that they have no platform to express their concerns and no voice to affect policy debates or demand a fairer share of society's goods.

Homi K. Bhabha: Homi K. Bhabha's theory is based on the existence of such a space where cultural borders open up to each other, and the creation of a new hybrid culture that combines their features and atones for their differences. Homi K Bhabha, inextricably linked to specific words. There is his

concept of cultural hybridity, which holds that world cultures are not fully formed and distinct entities, but rather malleable entities that are constantly being shaped.

The key concepts in postcolonial critical theory:

Ambivalence: the ambiguous relationship between colonizer and colonized.

Alterity: is defined as "the state of being different or other"; the political, cultural, linguistic, or religious other.

Colonial education: The process by which a colonizing power assimilates a subaltern

Diaspora. Diaspora literature is frequently concerned with maintaining or changing one's identity, language, and culture while living in another culture or country.

Essentialism: The essence or "whatness" of something is defined as essentialism. **Ethnicity:** a fusion of traits associated with a group-shared set of values, beliefs, norms, tastes, behaviors, experiences, memories, and loyalties.

Exoticism: the process by which a cultural practice is made stimulating and exciting **Hegemony:** the ability of the ruling class through economic and political control

Hybridity: the emergence of new of cross-cultural exchange.

Ideology is defined as "a set of shared values, beliefs, or ideas held by a social group

Language: In the context of colonialism and post colonialism, language has frequently served as both colonization and resistance.

Magical realism: The adaptation of Western realist literary methods to describe the imaginary life of indigenous cultures.

Mapping; the mapping of global space in the context of colonialism was both prescriptive and descriptive.

Meta narrative: a large cultural story that attempts to explain all of the small, local narratives within its border

Mimicry: the process by which the colonized adapt the culture (language, education, clothing, etc.) of the colonize

Nation/nation n state: is a group of people united under a single government.

Orientalism: the process by which "the Orient" was constructed as an exotic other by European studies and culture

Other: the social and/or psychological mechanisms by which one group excluded. **Race** The distribution and classification of human beings based on physical and biological characteristics is known as race.."

Space/place: A geographic locale is represented by space.

Subaltern: a member of the lower or colonized classes

Gender: Postcolonial gender discourse discusses the double colonization of women by both imperialism and patriarchy

History: the nations are increasingly interested and keen on writing about their native histories,

Double Consciousness: A major concept formulated by double consciousness echoes contention of the black skin and white skin.

Neocolonialism: Neocolonialism refers to the continuing economic dominance and exploitation of the "politically-free".

Bharati Mukerji's 'Jasmine' as a prototype: The postcolonial Diaspora of the mid- to late-twentieth century is an important aspect of postcolonial engagement. The scenario elaborates on issues such as marginalization, cultural insularity, and social isolation, disparities, racism, ethnicity, etc. The migrants from the new world are constantly engaged in a psychological battle. Bharathi Mukherjee's *Jasmine*, with its postcolonial undercurrent, represents the English language, Western culture, enlightenment, and progress. 'Jasmine' portrays the protagonist as a postcolonial woman who is not always stereotypically silenced by hegemonic narrative. Jasmine is seen as plainly advancing the counter-discursive agenda of postcolonial feminism. The path of Jasmine's gradual assertion of her right to speak is problematic from the standpoint of post-colonial feminist politics, because Jasmine is sometimes guilty of self-consolidating presentations of the "other" that replicate the "colonizing" impulse. Jasmine, as protagonist and narrator, feels and expresses a great deal of ambivalence about her racial, social, and sexual identities.

Mukherjee's *Jasmine* investigates issues of history, identity, culture, gender, and immigration. Many of the attitudes toward Indian and North American culture that shape *Jasmine's* development as a postcolonial. *Jasmine's* post-colonial cultural legacies are visible in the mode of intervention she chooses. Her particular socio-cultural legacy has not only provided her with an education and a language in which to express her dissatisfaction, but it has also provided her with a platform to do so. Her particular socio-cultural legacy has provided her with not only an education and a language to express her dissatisfaction, but also a narrative mode

Conclusion: Post colonialism, the historical period or state of affairs following Western colonialism; the term can also be used to describe the concurrent project to reclaim and rethink the history and agency of people subordinated under various forms of imperialism. Post colonialism has gone through and continues to go through three broad stages as a body of theory and a study of political and cultural change: an initial recognition of the social, psychological, and cultural inferiority imposed by colonization the battle for ethnic, cultural, and political independence.

References:

1. Said,Edward. *Orientalism:Western Conceptions of the Orient* (1978).
2. Ghosh, Amitav. "The Diaspora in Indian Culture" Delhi:Ravi Dayal Publ.&Permanent Black,2002.
3. Bhabha, Homi. *The Location of Culture*. London:Routledge,1994
4. Mukherjee,Bharati.. — *Jasmine*. NewYork :Viking,1989..
5. Said,Edward. *Orientalism:Western Conceptions of the Orient* (1978). 3rd edn.Harmondsworth: Penguin,1991.
6. Said Edward ,*Cultural Imperialism*, 1993.
7. Gayathri Chakravthy Spivak, *the Post Colonial Critic*, 1990.
8. A Critical Overview of Literary Criticism in English Literature by simhachalam Thamarana-
aritle,